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Constraints of Online Learning Using Google Classroom During Covid-19

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to connect the learning school of computer education students at Dehasen University Bengkulu in using google class. This type of research is descriptive qualitative. Respondents' answers using the google form application. Data were analyzed by stages of reduction, display and conclusion drawing or verification. The google form questionnaire was used as an instrument used to collect data in this study. The results of the analysis show that students face some difficulties in using google classroom on the attendance menu, quiz assignment menu, essay assignment menu, word or pdf download menu and video download menu. To overcome these obstacles, teachers need to learn Google Classroom in accordance with the obstacles they are facing. Application of this study: This research can be useful at Dehasen University Bengkulu which is currently implementing online learning, Place in Bengkulu city, Bengkulu Province, Field of study Computer education. The novelty in this research is that the researcher conducts research to see from the constraints of the menus that are on google scholar, which can be useful for educators, both lecturers or teachers in using the google classroom application and can provide knowledge about obstacles in the online learning process using google classroom, so that when a teacher or lecturer wants to use google classroom, they have prepared a solution to face these obstacles. To advance this study, further research is needed. This research is new knowledge in the Image Capturing Engineering course.

Keywords: Google Classroom, Online, Computer Education

1. Introduction

During the Covid 19 pandemic according to a circular from the Ministry of Education and Culture, Directorate of Higher Education No.1 of 2020 regarding the prevention of the spread of covid-19 in the world of education, students still have to carry out the learning process at home (Handarini & Wulandari, 2020). This Covid has a direct impact on the world of education, therefore it is necessary to close educational institutions so that the corona virus does not spread (Aji, 2020)

The process of lecturing activities must continue to be carried out so it is necessary to do face-to-face learning substitutes with online learning. Online learning is learning that is carried out using the internet as a means of transferring knowledge to students (Handarini & Wulandari, 2020), Online learning is a learning process that utilizes technology virtually by using the internet which is not done face-to-face but electronic media as a means of assistance (Syarifudin, 2020). Online learning can be a solution for lecturers to deliver material to students in the Covid-19 pandemic. Where in the press conference of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia, through a video guide for organizing learning for the 2020/2021 academic year, universities must conduct lectures online ([https: kompas.com](https://kompas.com)).

The advantage of online learning is that it can be anywhere and anytime it can make online learning more effective and flexible (Syarifudin, 2020), can learn independently using the help of the internet (Megawanti, 2020), can be more proficient in information technology because they have been trained to master applications (Pangondian et al., 2019).

There is also a lack of online learning : limitations to doing practical learning so that learning is more to theory than practice (Sanjaya, 2020), the difficulty of buying quotas for the internet (Anggianita et al., 2020), features on mobile phones that have limitations (Anugrahana, 2020), parents come from the middle to lower economy, so there is no money to buy a cellphone (Asmuni, 2020), and because they do not have a quota, the assignment collection is late (Ramanta & Widayanti, 2020).

Based on the results of the initial semester meeting which was held on Friday 11th of the month of 2020 between the head of the Dehasen Bengkulu University Computer Education study program and the Lecturers, which was attended by the study program chairman, the study program secretary and 6 lecturers teaching computer education courses at Dehasen University Bengkulu, it was decided to online learning using the google classroom application. Google Classroom is one of the free accesses that makes it easier for lecturers and students in the e-learning process, which offers many benefits for its users (Hapsari & Pamungkas, 2019). He reasons for using google classroom are based on good response analysis shown by students in using Google Classroom, so that Google Classroom can be used to help smooth the learning process (Utami, 2019), but the requirements that need to be taken into account if you want to use google classroom are the need for good internet access (Rozak & Albantani, 2018).

The weaknesses of google classroom are that if the google drive is full, we cannot send files (Nurhusna, 2020). Another drawback is that google classroom can only be accessed via a google account, does not have a share link menu to recommend or add other people to join the google classroom class (Santosa et al., 2020), and there is no direct practice, only theory (Aditya, 2020).

Students of Bengkulu Dehasen University Computer Education come from several areas, namely North Bengkulu district, South Bengkulu district, Seluma district, Rejang Lebong district, Kepahyang district, Kaur district, Muara Aman district, Muko-Muko district and some are from Bengkulu city. The difference from the geographical location of residence has an impact on the online learning process, and will raise obstacles in the online learning process (Juliya & Herlambang, 2021). Differences in geographical locations can cause obstacles in online learning (Rigianti, 2020).

Based on information obtained from computer education students at the University of Dehasen Bengkulu, if there is a blackout in their area, especially those who live in the area, then their signal will be disturbed and even lost, power outages in the student area live sometimes die from morning to evening so that the internet network will be disturbed. Online learning in the midst of the Covid-19 pandemic situation, there are many obstacles, bad network, blackout causes the signal to disappear (Fauziyah, 2020).

Previous research only looked at online learning barriers in general (Jamaluddin et al., 2020), the implementation of online learning (Syarifudin, 2020), the impact of covid on the implementation of online learning (Dewi, 2020), online learning based on Google Classroom (Suhada et al., 2020), utilizing google classroom (Hapsari & Pamungkas, 2019). Without examining the obstacles that occur when using google classroom. Because it is seen

the importance of this, it is necessary to carry out further research with the title "constraints of online learning using google classroom during covid 19 computer education students at Dehasen University Bengkulu?"

2. Research Methods

This study uses a qualitative approach with a descriptive design. A qualitative approach is an approach taken by a researcher to the research subject in a complete manner where there is an actual incident and the researcher is used as a key instrument in the study, then the results of the approach obtained are explained in the form of a description of words written in accordance with actual data and generalization is not too emphasized but more emphasized on its meaning (Raco, 2018).

Focus examines the constraints of using google classroom. This research was conducted for one semester. Some of the variables included in the focus of the study were student attendance, quiz assignments, essay assignments, downloading material in word or pdf form, and downloading material in the form of videos.

The data source of this research is the computer education students of Bengkulu University, semester 3, totaling 40 people, taken this class because they come from various regions.

The research instrument in this study consisted of: a questionnaire via Google Form, a google form data recap and a data recap folder. Answers to questionnaires from respondents that are automatically recorded in the system are converted into excel tabulations for further processing or analysis. Data analysis techniques are inductive, in the formation of abstracts based on data items that have been collected, then they are grouped based on the information that has been obtained then become the conclusions in the research. The stages of descriptive analysis are reduction, display and conclusion drawing / verification (Miles et al., 2018).

3. Research Results and Discussion

Research result

The number of respondents recorded via google form in this study were 30 respondents. The menus used for the student's google classroom are attendance, quiz assignments, essay assignments, and material in the form of word or pdf, material in the form of video. The percentage details of respondents are as follows :

a. Attendance

Figure 1: Attendance Filling

For absenteeism filling in google room, 5 people experienced interference during their absence, and 25 people never experienced interference. This is caused by signal interference, when doing absences so that it is considered absent.

Based on the results of interviews with the five respondents: this happens if attendance is limited to 30 minutes starting from the lecture schedule.

b. Quiz assignments

Figure 2: Completion of quiz assignments

For the task in the form of quizzes, 23 people have experienced problems, while 7 people have never experienced problems. This is caused by signal interference.

Based on the results of the interview to conclude, this happens if the time for the quiz is limited to 30 minutes and there are many questions that have to be done, so there is less time to think about the right answer where the signal constraint becomes an obstacle to switching to another question.

c. Essay assignment

Figure 3: Essay Task

For work on assignments in the form of an essay, 10 people had experienced problems, while 23 people had never experienced problems. This is caused by signal interference.

Based on the results of interviews with respondents, it was observed : This happens when lectures are held at night or in the evening and sometimes there is a power outage, then given the assignment and given a fairly short time limit for the task.

d. Download material in word or pdf format

Figure 5: Downloading material in word or pdf format

To download an assignment in word or pdf form 15 people have experienced problems, while 15 people have never experienced problems.

Based on the results of interviews with respondents : this happens if the material is given in the afternoon or evening, sometimes in some areas there are blackouts.

e. Download material in the form of videos

Figure 6: Downloading material in video form

Downloading material in the form of video 25 people have experienced problems, while 5 people have never experienced problems.

Based on the results of interviews with respondents : this happens because in their area the signal is not stable so it takes a long time to download material in the form of a video.

Discussion

The lecture schedule is given freedom by the university so that lecturers can conduct it in the morning, during the day, at night, but for the morning at 08.00 western Indonesian time and at night the maximum time is 22.00 western Indonesian time. One of the advantages of online learning is that the lecture schedule is more flexible to use when lecturing online (Jamil & Aprilisanda, 2020). However, what students feel is if the lecture is held in the afternoon or evening, sometimes there are frequent power cuts causing their signal to be lost and sometimes there is weather disturbance which causes the signal to be unstable.

As a lecture rule from Dehasen Bengkulu University, every lecturer must make a form for student absences in google classroom. Then the student attendance form is screenshot as evidence that the lecturer has carried out online learning activities submitted to the computer education study program, and the lecturer is asked to set a time limit on the absent form, with the aim of making students more disciplined and on time. This absent form will also later serve as a reference for grading students.

The Dehasen Bengkulu University asked lecturers who taught courses to provide teaching materials to students in google classroom, with the aim that students can download the material and study the material that has been shared by lecturers on the google scholar material menu.

Regarding the material distributed on the google classroom material menu, lecturers are free to provide material in any form, it can be in the form of words, pdf, and power points. The form of evidence of providing material will also later become material for reports that have carried out lectures. The size of the word, pdf, and powerpoint files is also not limited to being completely left to the lecturers.

Specifically for practical subjects, the head of the Dehasen University computer education study program, Bengkulu, asked lecturers to provide material in the form of video media. One of the reasons why choosing video media is that it can increase learning motivation after using video as a learning medium (Umairah & Zulfah, 2020). The video media made must be related to the teaching material, the file size for the video is not determined by how much it is submitted to the respective lecturers. Making video media can use power point, use android or use other equipment.

Lecturers give assignments in the form of quizzes and essays on google form to see the extent to which students understand the material that has been given. In this quiz, there is a time limit for both quiz questions and essay questions, and the questions made must be in accordance with the lecture material given by the lecturer in question. Questions can be given before learning begins, in the learning process and after the learning process. Assessment in the form of a quiz or essay can also be applied to the midterm exam at the eighth meeting and the final semester exam held at the sixteenth meeting.

Figure 7: Recapitulation of results using google classroom

Based on Figure 7. It can be seen that the one experiencing the biggest problem is the quiz task, then it is followed in downloading the word or pdf material, and finally downloading the video material. This is due to internet disruption. Internet disruption is an obstacle in almost all online learning, both at the primary school and college levels, (Hutauruk & Sidabutar, 2020). This also happened in Aceh Besar Province, the problem was that the electricity often went out which caused the laptop to not be used and the decision was that it could not download learning media in the form of youtube, word or pdf (Sahelatua et al., 2018).

For attendance and essay assignments, it appears that there are obstacles, but they are not too high compared to the three items. Attendance constraints, because the time to do absences in google classroom is too short, causing students to be absent late so they are considered absent, this of course will affect the value of the student in the attendance assessment item. For essay assignments, the questions given are too many, causing students to sometimes need time to work on them and when they want to send coursework on Google Form there is a signal disturbance that finally the assignment cannot be submitted anymore because the time given has run out, so they are certainly not getting a grade on task appraisal item because it is deemed not to have collected the task.

Conclusion

The use of Google classroom has several obstacles: if there is a power outage, the use of google classroom will be disrupted, student attendance becomes a problem if the time given for absences is too short, downloading videos is hampered because the signal is sometimes unstable and the video size is too large causing it to take a long time to download it.

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